

Spectrophotometric determination of ornidazole

B. H. M. Mruthyunjayaswamy^{a*}, S. M. Mali Patil^a and S. Appala Raju^b

^aDepartment of Chemistry, Gulbarga University, Gulbarga-585 106, India

E-mail : bhmmswamy@rediffmail.com

^bH. K. E. S.'s College of Pharmacy, Gulbarga-585 105, India

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Three simple, sensitive, selective and economical methods (method A, B and C) for the determination of ornidazole have been described. Method A, B and C are based on the formation of yellow, blood red and blue coloured chromogens when reduced ornidazole *in situ* reacted with vanillin, 1,10-phenanthroline in presence of ferric ions and Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagents exhibiting λ_{\max} at 426, 508.8 and 648 nm, respectively, which obeyed Beer's law in the concentration range of 5–25, 2–10 and 5–25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. The results of analysis for the three methods have been validated statistically and by recovery studies. The results are comparable with those obtained with UV spectrophotometric method in alcohol at 312.8 nm.

Ornidazole¹, 1-chloro-3-(2-methyl-5-nitroimidazole-1-yl) propan-2-ol, is one of the large series of nitroimidazoles used in the treatment of amoebiasis, giardiasis and anaerobic infections. Few methods have been reported for the determination of ornidazole which include HPLC², UV³ and visible⁴ spectrophotometric techniques. In the present investigations, we have developed, three simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods for the quantitative estimation of ornidazole after converting it into its reduced form *in situ* by zinc granules and hydrochloric acid in alcohol at RT. The complete conversion of ornidazole to its reduced form *in situ* has been confirmed by the disappearance of a peak at 312.8 nm in its UV spectrum which was a characteristic peak in the UV spectrum of ornidazole itself in alcohol.

Results and discussion

The presence of amino group, in reduced ornidazole, 1-chloro-3-(2-methyl-5-aminoimidazole-1-yl) propan-2-ol enabled the use of its condensation reaction with vanillin forming yellow coloured Schiff's base (Scheme 1) exhibiting λ_{\max} at 426 nm. In method B, reduced ornidazole *in situ* reduces ferric ions to ferrous ions which react with 1,10-phenanthroline to form a blood red coloured complex with λ_{\max} 508.8 nm. Method C is based on the reduction of the heteropoly acid, phosphomolybdotungstic acid, the well known Folin-Ciocalteu (FC) reagent by the reduced ornidazole *in situ* in the presence of an alkali thereby producing one or more of possible reduced species which have a characteristic intense blue colour with

λ_{\max} 648 nm. In methods A, B and C Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 5–25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 2–10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and 5–25 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively. The very fact that neither reduced ornidazole nor reagents used displayed any peaks at 426, 508.8 and 648 nm respectively, proves beyond doubt that the reduced ornidazole has undergone reactions *in situ* quantitatively with the above reagents.

Scheme 1

The optical characteristics such as Beer's law limits, absorption maxima, molar absorptivity, Sandell's sensitivity, percent relative standard deviation (calculated from the eight measurements containing 3/4th of the amount of the upper Beer' law limits or ornidazole) and percent

Note

Table 1. Optical characteristics and precision

	Method A	Method B	Method C
λ_{\max} (nm)	426	508.8	648
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$) (C)	5–25	2–10	5–25
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	0.526×10^4	1.522×10^4	0.550×10^4
Sandell's sensitivity : ($\mu\text{g/cm}^{-2}$ –0.001 absorption units)	0.027	0.031	0.024
Regression equation ($y = a + bc$) ^a :			
Slope (b)	2.373×10^{-2}	6.709×10^{-2}	2.461×10^{-2}
Intercept (a)	1.550×10^{-3}	1.459×10^{-2}	0.865×10^{-2}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9989	0.9998	0.9997
% RSD	1.0825	0.8688	1.1297
Range of errors ^b :			
Confidence limits with 0.05 level	± 0.004345	± 0.004010	± 0.004685
Confidence limits with 0.01 level	± 0.006428	± 0.005933	± 0.006932

^a Y is the absorbance and C is the concentration in $\mu\text{g/ml}$.

^bFor eight measurements.

Table 2. Estimation of ornidazole in pharmaceutical formulations

Sample	Labelled amount in (mg)	Amount obtained (mg)			UV method	% Recovery of proposed methods ^b		
		Method A	Method B	Method C		Method A	Method B	Method C
1	500	499.89	498.30	498.74	499.85	99.96	99.42	99.32
2	500	499.97	498.75	498.96	499.90	99.90	99.72	99.50
3	500	498.95	499.20	498.90	499.65	99.97	99.57	99.63

^aAverage of eighth determinations.

^bRecovery of amount added to the pharmaceutical formulation (average of three determinations).

range of error (0.05 and 0.01 confidence limits) were calculated for the three methods and the results are summarised in Table 1. The optimum conditions for colour development for method A, B and C have been established by varying the parameters one at a time and keeping the other parameters fixed and observing the effects of product on the absorbance of the coloured species and incorporated in the procedures. The values obtained for the determination of ornidazole in different brands of tablets samples 1, 2 and 3 by the proposed and UV methods are compared in Table 2. To evaluate the validity and reproducibility of the methods, known amounts of pure drug were added to the previously analysed pharmaceutical preparations and the mixtures were analysed by the proposed methods. The percent recoveries are given in Table 2.

These studies revealed that the common excipients and other additives such as lactose, starch, gelatin, talc and magnesium stearate, that are usually present in the tablet dosage forms did not interfere at their regularly added

levels.

Experimental

A Systronics 119 spectrophotometer was used.

Purified or analytical grade samples were used.

Ornidazole (pure or formulation) (~100 mg) was accurately weighed and dissolved in alcohol (20 ml) and treated with 5 *N* HCl (10 ml) and zinc granules (0.8 g) in portions were added while stirring. After standing for 1 h at RT, the solution was filtered, the residue washed with alcohol (3 × 10 ml) and the total volume of the filtrate was brought to 100 ml with alcohol (1 mg/ml). The final concentration of reduced ornidazole was brought to 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ with alcohol.

Assay :

Method A : Aliquots (0.5–2.5 ml) of reduced ornidazole (1 ml = 100 μg) were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each, vanillin (1 ml; 0.5 % w/v), in alcohol, conc. HCl (2 drops) were added and heated at

70° on a water-bath for 20 min. After cooling, the volume was brought upto the mark with alcohol and the absorbance of the yellow coloured species was measured at 426 nm against reagent blank. The coloured species was stable for more than 12 h. At alkaline pH, colour started fading. The amount of ornidazole was computed from calibration curve.

Method B : Aliquots (0.2–1 ml) of reduced ornidazole (1 ml = 100 µg) were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each, ferric chloride (0.5 ml; 0.03 M) and 1,10-phenanthroline solution (0.5 ml, 0.5%, w/v) in alcohol were added and heated on a water-bath for 25 min and then cooled to RT. To each flask, *o*-phosphoric acid solution (2 ml; 0.02 M) was added and final volume was made upto 10 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the blood red coloured species formed was measured at 508.8 nm against the reagent blank. The absorbance of reaction product at 508.8 nm remains stable for 4 h after final dilution. The amount of ornidazole present in the sample solution was computed from its calibration curve.

Method C : Aliquots (0.5–2.5 ml) of reduced ornidazole (1 ml = 100 µg) were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. To each, sodium hydroxide solution (3 ml; 0.5 N) and FC reagent (1 ml; 0.5 N) were added and mixed well. The total volume of each flask was made upto 10 ml with distilled water. The resultant solution was centrifuged to remove the precipitate formed. The absorbance of blue coloured chromogen in the centrifugate was measured at 648 nm against reagent blank. This chromogen remains stable for 6 h. The amount of ornidazole

present in the sample solution was computed from its calibration curve.

The results of the above methods are compared with the results obtained with UV spectrophotometric method. In UV method, solution of ornidazole in alcohol either pure or formulation (100 µg/ml), was prepared. Aliquotes of ornidazole ranging from 0.2–1 ml (1 ml = 100 µg) were transferred into a series of 10 ml volumetric flasks. The volume was made upto the mark with alcohol and the absorbance of the solutions was measured at 312.8 nm against solvent blank. The amount of ornidazole was computed from calibration graph.

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